

Shannon's Entropy and a Probability Response to a Stimulus

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In the literature, it is suggested that one can maximize Shannon's entropy $-\sum_i P_i \ln(P_i)$ subject to constraints in order to obtain probability distributions such as the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution etc. It is suggested that this is a purely statistical approach which does not rely on physics (1). The $\ln(P_i)$ is associated with information.

In this note, we consider the possibility that $\ln(P_i)$ may be associated with a probability response to a stimulus. In physics, P_i is often associated with a probability density $d(x)$ or $d(v)$ such as a physical density. Once one has found the optimum $d(x)$, one can take a derivative (for example a spatial derivative) of $\ln(d(x))$ namely $d[\ln(d(x))] = d[d(x)] / d(x)$. This is normally part of an equation of the form $A(x) d[d(x)] + B(x) d(x) = 0$. It seems that such an equation can be thought of as a "change" in the density $d(x)$ which offsets a stimulus $B(x)$ multiplied by $d(x)$. Here $d(x)$ is the density and so $B(x)d(x)$ is a kind of average stimulus effect which appears in many cases. Thus, the optimal $d(x)$ is a solution of a differential equation, and not necessarily the result of the maximization of entropy (although it can be written that way if one knows the correct constraint to use). The point may be that the differential equation is based on physical conditions which are important. Once these are understood, one can reformulate the problem as a maximization one using "appropriate" constraints which are really based on key physical ideas.

In this note, we attempt to examine the classical mechanical case, the velocity and spatial statistical mechanical cases and the quantum case to a certain degree.

Classical Mechanical Case

In classical mechanics, one can describe a particle moving under a force by a density $1/v(x)$ (2) where $\int v(x) \cdot v(x) + V(x) = E$. In order for the maximization of Shannon's entropy to apply, one would need to maximize an equation of the form: $-d(x) \ln[d(x)] + b \ln[v(x)]$ where b is a Lagrange multiplier. It is not clear why one would choose $\ln[v(x)]$ as a constraint. In terms of a stimulus, one might say that a force $-dV(x)/dx$ is acting on one particle, but there is no density in such a picture.

Consider the case of flux, namely the number of particles per second moving along x . Here x is broken into equally spaced dx pieces. There is only one particle, so flux = $1/dt$ where dt is the time for the particle to move through dx . dt is different for different speeds. Thus,

$$\text{flux} = 1/dt = 1 v(x)/dx = d(x) dx/dx v = d(x) v(x) ((1))$$

If the flux is not constant, it seems that this would imply a source or sink of particles so: flux = constant. Here the density $d(x)$ really represents an unnormalized probability. Imagine that time is broken into equally spaced units of $\Delta(t)$. Then a time probability = $dt / \Delta(t)$ and this is written as $d(x) dx / \Delta(t)$.

Consider ((1)) written as $d[d(x)] v(x) + d(x) d[v(x)] = 0$. Then $d[v(x)]$ can be thought of as the stimulus (which is like an acceleration) multiplied by the density $d(x)$. The density has to change $d[d(x)]$ to counteract this stimulus. Note that if one divides by $v(x)$, then one has $d[v(x)]/v(x)$ which is $d[\ln[d(x)]]$ which is the constraint in the Shannon's entropy expression. Here it appears from physical considerations.

[Another way to consider this situation is to argue that for a velocity the separation of two particles in a small dt becomes proportional to vdt , with dt being a constant. The density is $1/\text{separation}$ and so is proportional to $1/v(x)$.]

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Velocity Distribution

In (1), it is argued that a distribution of the form of a Maxwell-Boltzmann velocity distribution $P(v) = C \exp(-.5mv^2/T)$ can be obtained strictly from maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint:

Integral on v $P(v)(v-\text{vave})^2 = \text{sigma}$.

This would require no "physics". Alternative arguments in the literature state that the Gaussian is due to the Central Limit Theorem. Boltzmann developed a transport equation which yields an equilibrium condition of:

$$P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_3)P(p_4) \quad ((2))$$

Here p_i is a momentum and $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$ where these are vectors. Condition ((2)) can be written only using the notion of independent probabilities. One needs to have a p_1 and p_2 and the probability of an "and" condition is $P(p_1) * P(p_2)$. There is no physics at this point, other than that the collisions between two particles occur and probabilities are independent, it seems. A solution to ((2)) is $P(p_1) = a^{-\text{function}(p_1)}$ where $\text{function}(p_1)$ is conserved. Here a is a constant which be chosen to be e for convenience. Kinetic energy is conserved in elastic collisions so this can be used, thus leading to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

In (3), it is argued that one can start with $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_3)P(p_4)$ and obtain:
 $d \ln(f(p))/dp (1/p) = \text{constant}$. This can be written in the form:

$$d f(p) = C p f(p) \quad ((3))$$

This is of the form of a flux $pf(p)$ as the stimulus being countered by $d f(p)$ in a kind of action-reaction way. It is again of the form of the stimulus reaction.

Spatial part of Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

The spatial part of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is written as $\exp(-V(x)/T)$ times a normalization constant. In statistical mechanics textbooks (4), this result is often obtained using

a balance pressure holding a little box of gas acted upon by a force $F(x)$. Thus, $F(x) d(x)$ is the stimulus part of the equation. Using the ideal gas law leads to:

$$\text{Pressure difference} = RT \frac{d(x)}{dx} = F(x) d(x) \quad ((5))$$

This is again the same form as in earlier cases. The physical density $d(x)$ has to change in order to counteract $F(x) d(x)$. This is a differential equation based directly on the physical idea of force balance. Now, one may ask: Where is the dynamics in such an equation? Gas particles acted upon by a force should accelerate. It seems that one could formulate ((5)) using such a picture. $F(x) d(x)$ can be written as $ma(x) d(x)$ where $a(x)$ is the acceleration for each particle regardless of its speed in a little box. This extra velocity should lead to extra pressure which is compensated by a change in $d(x)$ density, which is allowable in a gas because there are many particles and spatial density can be changed. It is as if the gas, which is in velocity equilibrium, senses an increase in kinetic energy or pressure due to collective kinetic energy being picked up and adjusts its density accordingly.

Quantum Mechanics

In quantum mechanics, one deals with $W(x)$ a wavefunction, although there is still a spatial density $d(x)=W(x)W(x)$. It is argued in (5) that $P(p/x)= \int p \sin(px) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \int p \sin(px)$, so $W(x)$ is a unnormalized sum of relative probabilities.

Consider $d \frac{d(x)}{dx} = 2 W(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$. This is a flux picture. In the ground state of a harmonic oscillator $2 W(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = 2 \left[\frac{d}{dx} V(x) \right] d(x)$ which is exactly the stimulus response picture. Thus, there seems to be a direct link between the quantum oscillator ground state and the classical statistical mechanical one is this "response to a stimulus" picture. In general, for other $V(x)$ potentials in quantum mechanics, things are different. Let us attempt to consider why.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 W(x)}{dx^2} \right] + \frac{d}{dx} V(x) W(x) + V(x) \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = E \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad \text{or}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2 W(x)}{dx^2} \right] + \frac{d}{dx} V(x) = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 \frac{d}{dx} W(x)$$

Here $\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2$ is the classical kinetic energy at point x .

Quantum mechanics preserves average kinetic energy plus $V(x) = E$ at each point x , but one does not have a localized particle.

Let us see more closely what is happening in quantum mechanics

$$\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \frac{d^3 W(x)}{dx^3} / W(x) = \frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = \text{classical kinetic energy}$$

One can now take d/dx of both sides to obtain:

$$\left(-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \right) \frac{d^4 W(x)}{dx^4} / W(x) + \frac{d^3 W(x)}{dx^3} / W(x)^2 \frac{d}{dx} W(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{1}{2} m v(x)^2 \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \right)$$

$$(-1/2m) \text{del}^3 W(x) / W(x) + .5mv(x)v(x) d/dx \ln(W(x)) = d/dx (.5mv(x)*v(x)) = - d/dx V(x)$$

Or

$$(-1/2m) \text{del}^3 W(x) / W(x) = - .5mv(x)v(x) d/dx \ln(W(x)) - d/dx V(x) \quad ((6))$$

This is similar to the stimulus type equation in previous cases with $d/dx \ln(W(x))$ instead of $d/dx \ln(d(x))$, but in quantum mechanics there is an extra term containing the gradient cubed.

For the ground state of the quantum oscillator the first term combines with the other two to give the stimulus type equation found in classical and statistical mechanics.

[It has been pointed out in (6), that for the ground state of an oscillator $V(x)W(x)W(x)$ is of the form of Shannon's entropy because $W(x)=\exp(-ax*x)$ so $V(x) = \ln(W(x)W(x))*C$ where C is a constant. Thus, for this case, it looks like one is maximizing a Schrodinger density to obtain the Schrodinger equation. The Schrodinger equation, however, is a differential equation and for the ground state E, there is only one function $W(x)$ which yields an expectation energy of E.]

Conclusion

In conclusion, although one can maximize Shannon's entropy subject to constraints, it is suggested in this note that there is a physical action-reaction occurring such that a stimulus $B(x)$ time $d(x)$ density is offset by a change in density $d(x)$ for classical and statistical mechanics. (This also lets one know which constraint to use.) This action-reaction involving d [$\ln(d(x))$] also holds for the ground state of a quantum mechanical oscillator, but in general for quantum mechanics the stimulus equation is modified by an extra term of the form of $(-1/2m)$ gradient cubed $W(x)$ divided by $W(x)$.

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